

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND ENERGY ABSORPTION BEHAVIOUR OF POLYMER-NANOCOMPOSITES

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of the nanofillers percentage on the nanocomposites quasi-static and dynamic behaviour. The effect of the type of nanofillers used was also discussed. Polyamide-6 reinforced by 30wt.% of glass fibre and with an addition of nanoclay (Organically modified Montmorillonite: O-MMT) or nanosilica (SiO₂) were tested in order to characterise their tensile properties. Crashing behaviour and energy absorption capabilities were analysed by compression and dynamic crash of cones structures. The results show that integration of secondary nanofillers is a good way to enhance the mechanical properties of PA composites; however the percentage and type of filler play a crucial point. The augmentation of O-MMT content involves a decrease in tensile properties, and an optimum at 1wt.% was found for SiO₂-nanocomposites. However for both types of nano-fillers, the crashing behaviour and energy absorption in dynamic tests was enhanced with increase in nano-fillers percentage. It is also shown that the brittleness behaviour of nanocomposites is led by the interaction matrix/fibre, which is dependant of the nano-filler type.

Keywords: *three-phase Nanocomposites; Polyamide-6; Energy Absorption; Impact*

1 General Introduction

Nowadays, car manufacturers aim to produce lightweight vehicles in order to reduce their fuel's consumption and CO₂ emissions. To achieve this goal, they tend to replace metallic parts by the use of polymeric materials.

These materials present many others advantages like recyclability, resistance to corrosion and chemical attack, ease of manufacturing, low cost of production and part integration.

However, their bad impact properties and capacities to absorb energy prevent polymeric materials from development for exterior or structural applications. To solve this problem, plastics are reinforced, usually with glass fibre, but it increase the density and the brittleness of the composite.

An alternative to glass fibre is to use nanofillers. Nanofillers are fillers with at least one dimension of less than 100 nanometres [1]. The nano-size allows an increase of contact's surface between matrix and filler and reduces stress concentrations around the filler, which results in enhanced properties. In more,

only 5wt.% of nanofillers can significantly improve behaviour and properties of a neat polymer [2], compared to at least 20wt.% with glass fibre.

The enhanced properties thanks to nanofillers addition are: higher heat-distortion temperature, scratch resistance, dimensional stability, water and thermal permeability, corrosion resistance, surface hardness, and electrical conductivity [1], [3].

Further, integration of nanofillers in polymers has also shown to improved stiffness, strength and modulus. Loading polyamide with 5% of Montmorillonite clay allows an increase of 40% for the tensile strength and of 70% for the modulus [Harmut Fischer, TNO, Netherlands].

Several parameters have a positive influence on these properties:

- An enhanced interaction between the matrix and the fillers, which involves a efficiently repartition of the load on the matrix and the fillers [4];
- A smaller size of the fillers, which reduces stress concentrations [5];
- The volume fraction of the fillers: it was reported that the strength and elongation at break was the best

at 5wt.% nano-fillers for the couple polyamide-6/SiO₂ [6];

- The filler shape: it changes the surface-to-volume ratio, which allows a better adhesion of the filler to the matrix when it increases [1].

The last improvement which nanofillers permit concerns the energy absorption and impact properties. As for the tensile properties, some parameters linked to the fillers permit to control these properties:

- Filler stiffness: it was found that an insertion of 22vol.% of elastic rubber with rigid calcium carbonate particles into a polyethylene matrix allows to enhance notch toughness by 16 times [7];
- Filler geometry: volume-to-surface ratio depends of the filler shape, which involves to enhanced the matrix-filler interaction;
- Filler volume fraction: it was shown that at low percentage of nanofillers (until 1wt.%), the notched Izod impact strength at 5°C was significantly improved for a polypropylene loading by O-MMT [8];
- Filler size: a compromise between too small particles, which can't reinforce the structure, and too big particles, which create stress concentration and facilitate cracks propagation is necessary. 200nm was found as the optimum for higher energy dissipation [9].

A third type of polymer-matrix composites exists: the three-phase composites, which are polymeric materials, reinforced by both micro and nano sized fillers. Some studies show that the combination of these fillers can significantly improve mechanical and impact properties. Wu et al. found that a polyamide-6/clay with 30wt.% of glass fibre had an enhanced tensile strength of 11% and a tensile modulus enhancement of 42% compared to polyamide-6/glass fibre [10]. Another work [11] reported that an addition of 2wt.% of SiO₂ nanoparticles in 30wt.% glass fibre/polyamide-6, improved the break by 32%. And it also changed the mode of failure of the structure, which involves better energy absorption capabilities.

In this work, mechanical and impact properties of polyamide-6/glass fibre with different weight percentages of Montmorillonite and nano-silica were investigated. The aim was to study the influence of the percentage of nanofillers on the nanocomposites

behaviour. The effect of the type of nanofillers used was also discussed.

2 Materials and Method

2.1 Materials and samples preparation

Two types of nanocomposites were produced: polyamide-6 (Durethan B30) reinforced by 30% of glass fibre (ThermoFlow672) and particles of SiO₂ (Aerosil R 974), and polyamide-6 reinforced by 30% of glass fibre and Montmorillonite (Dellite 43B). In total, seven materials were manufactured with different content of nano-fillers (Table 1). The nano-materials were obtained at Fraunhofer – Institute of Chemical Technology (Germany), by direct melting and extrusion in a twin-screw extruder at a maximum temperature of 280°C. The product was cooled in a water bath, pelletized and dried during 8 hours at 80°C. From granulates, samples (crash cones, tensile bars and plates, according to the standards) were injected moulded.

Table 1: Composition of the different studied nanocomposites

	Matrix Type (wt.%)	Glass Fibre Type (wt.%)	Filler Type (wt.%)
01	Durethan B30 (65)	ThermoFlow 672 (30)	Dellite 43B (5)
02	Durethan B30 (62.5)	ThermoFlow 672 (30)	Dellite 43B (7.5)
03	Durethan B30 (60)	ThermoFlow 672 (30)	Dellite 43B (10)
04	Durethan B30 (69)	ThermoFlow 672 (30)	Aerosil R 974 (1)
05	Durethan B30 (69.5)	ThermoFlow 672 (30)	Aerosil R 974 (0.5)
06	Durethan B30 (68.5)	ThermoFlow 672 (30)	Aerosil R 974 (1.5)
07	Durethan B30 (67)	ThermoFlow 673 (30)	Aerosil R 974 (3)

2.2 Mechanical testing

Three types of tests were carried out in order to characterise the mechanical and impact behaviour of the nanocomposites.

Tensile tests, according to the ISO527 standard (Plastics – Determination of tensile properties), were performed in the Instron 5500R electro-mechanical tensile-compression machine at ambient temperature. Seven specimens, flat dumb-bell type A, for each type of material were tested at a speed of 1mm/min. The load was measured with a 100kN load cell and the longitudinal displacement with a mechanical extensometer.

Crashing behaviour was analysed with quasi-static and dynamic crash experiments. Compression tests were carried out with the same machine than tensile tests. Crash cones samples were compressed at a speed of 0,1mm/s by 60mm at a room temperature. The load was recording with a 100kN load cell and the displacement with the captor of the crosshead.

Crash cones were also tested on dynamic crash with a high energy capacity drop tower rig machine. Impact tests were carried out at a speed of 4,4m/s, with a drop weight of 54kg, which is equivalent to an impact energy of 522J. The load was measured thanks to a 200kN load cell, placed under the sample and the crush length and displacement with a LVDT (Linear Variable Differential Transformer) displacement transducer.

2.3 Scanning Electron Mircrosopy

The fracture surfaces of the tensile bars were analysed with a scanning electron microscope (FEI XL 30) in order to understand the failure mechanism and the relation between the matrix and the filler. The samples were previously coated with gold to minimize charging of the sample.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Tensile Properties

Table 2: Tensile properties of the studied nanocomposites

	Nanofiller %	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Strain at break (%)
PA+GF [11]	0%	6.92	116.2	5.2
PA +	5%	9.15	101.8	1.73
GF + O-	7.5%	9.69	96.9	1.52
MMT	10%	9.76	85.4	1.16

PA + GF + SiO₂	0.5%	7.78	105.7	3.65
	1%	8.40	117.8	4.79
	1.5%	7.95	110.9	3.43
	3%	7.94	109.5	3.91

In this work, polyamide-6/Glass Fibre nanocomposites were prepared with an addition of different percentage of nano-fillers: 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 3wt.% of SiO₂, and 5, 7.5 and 10wt.% of O-MMT. The main results of the tests are resumed Table 2.

First observation is that the addition of a second filler, a nanosize one, significantly improve the Young's Modulus of the material compare to PA6 reinforced by 30wt.% of Glass Fibres tested by Silva et al. [11]. However, in the same time, it generally makes the material more brittle as, it involve a reduction of the tensile strength and strain at break.

Table 2 shows that the tensile modulus increased by the addition of more O-MMT, while the tensile strength and elongation at break decreased. The nanocomposite became more brittle when the percentage of O-MMT became higher.

Further, a different trend for the SiO₂-nanocomposites can be seen. All the properties (tensile modulus, strength and elongation at break) were improved when the SiO₂ content was 1wt.%, compared to 0.5wt.% of nano-fillers. Above this percentage, the properties underwent a slightly decrease and then stagnated. SiO₂-nanocomposites presented an optimum around 1wt.% of SiO₂ content.

Figure 1: Tensile stress vs strain curves for polyamide-6/glass fibre/O-MMT at different content

Figure 2: Tensile stress vs strain curves for polyamide-6/glass fibre/SiO₂ at different content

The results also indicate a difference in the behaviour between O-MMT-nanocomposites and SiO₂-nanocomposites (Figure 1; Figure 2). The polyamide-6/Glass Fibre/O-MMT was less able to be deformed, the stress vs strain curves report a brittle behaviour with only elastic deformation. Whereas, the SiO₂-nanocomposites were less brittle, the curves present a beginning of plastic deformation before breaking.

3.2 Crashing behaviour

The crashing behaviour was studied with quasi-static and dynamic crash tests. The results are resumed in Table 3 and Table 4. One way to classify the failure mode was identify by Silva et al. [11]: Mode I – progressive crushing with micro-fragmentation and delamination, Mode II – brittle fracture with large fragmentation and failure, Mode III – brittle but progressive crushing with medium fragmentation.

Table 3: Quasi-static characteristics of the nanocomposites structures

	Collapse Mode	Initial Peak (kN)	Energy absorbed (kJ)	Specific Energy (kJ/kg)
PA+GF+O-MMT 5%	III	42.17	1.752	28.27
PA+GF+O-MMT 7.5%	III	37.57	1.443	22.23
PA+GF+O-MMT	III	35.17	1.562	24.49

10%				
PA+GF+SiO ₂ 0.5%	III	40.04	1.545	24.13
PA+GF+SiO ₂ 1%	III	41.43	1.679	26.34
PA+GF+SiO ₂ 1.5%	III	40.82	1.654	25.72
PA+GF+SiO ₂ 3%	III	40.77	1.619	25.05

Table 4: Dynamic crashing characteristics of the nanocomposites structures

	Crush Length (mm)	Collapse Mode	Initial Peak (kN)	Energy absorbed (kJ)	Specific Energy (kJ/kg)
PA+GF+O-MMT 5%	17.87	III	69.86	0.364	12.83
PA+GF+O-MMT 7.5%	19.4	II	87.75	0.387	12.60
PA+GF+O-MMT 10%	24.23	III	63.40	0.438	12.77
PA+GF+SiO ₂ 0.5%	18.43	II	123.54	0.385	12.98
PA+GF+SiO ₂ 1%	18.01	II	113.46	0.354	13.48
PA+GF+SiO ₂ 1.5%	15.51	II	140.25	0.350	12.54
PA+GF+SiO ₂ 3%	14.76	I	121.40	0.405	14.69

The analysis of the results for the compressive experiments showed that all the nanocomposites had similar failure behaviour: brittle but progressive crushing with medium fragmentation (Figure 3-b). However, big cracks along the structure appeared in the cones made of Polyamide-6/Glass Fibre/O-MMT (Figure 3-a), which led to a reduction of absorbed energy.

In the case of axial dynamic crash, the samples in polyamide-6/Glass Fibre/O-MMT presented a better failure mode with the apparition of delamination (Figure 3-c), which involves an increase in energy absorption. And the energy absorption was better when the O-MMT content was higher.

On the opposite, crash cones with a low percentage of SiO₂ had a very bad way of fracture, which was brittle, produced large fragmentation resulting in catastrophic failure (Figure 3-d). But we also

noticed that the energy absorption was enhanced when the nano-fillers percentage was increased, and the structure in Polyamide-6/Glass Fibre and 3wt.% SiO₂, presented the best characteristics with an improve capacity of energy absorption and a fracture mode with delamination.

Figure 3: Crash cones reinforced by O-MMT, after compression test (a), after crash test (c), reinforced by nano-silica, after compression test (b), after crash test (d)

3.2 SEM Analysis

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the surface fracture of the polymer with the different nano-fillers. In the case of polyamide-6/Glass Fibre/O-MMT, a lot of pull-out of the fibre (Figure 4) could be seen. The fibres appear to be clean. The matrix underwent only elastic deformation hence the interaction between the glass fibre and the matrix was considerable weak. The opposite behaviour was found for, the materials with glass fibre and SiO₂, as the matrix was plastically deformed and interaction of fibres and matrix was good (Figure 5). The matrix seems to be attached to the fibres. Matrix/fibre relation was very strong and the glass fibres had to break, instead

of just pulling-out of the matrix. This explains the higher strength of nano-silica reinforced polyamide.

Figure 4: Fracture Surface of PA6/GF/O-MMT sample

Figure 5: Fracture Surface of PA6/GF/SiO₂ sample

4 Conclusions

The aim of this study was to identify the effect of the nano-fillers content on mechanical properties and failure behaviour.

It was shown that the increase of O-MMT percentage in polyamide-6/Glass Fibre composite made the material more brittle and had a negative effect on the tensile properties and quasi-static crashing behaviour. It could be explain by the weak interaction between the matrix and the fibres. However, in dynamic crash tests, these samples present a better way of failure, with delamination,

and the energy absorption increased with increasing O-MMT content.

About the nano-silica addition in polyamide-6/Glass Fibre, the nanocomposite with 1wt.% of SiO₂ presented the best tensile properties, and it is also the case for the quasi-static crashing behaviour. Further, the polyamide-6/Glass Fibre/3wt.%SiO₂, also has enhanced mechanical properties, as well as good failure mode, with delamination during dynamic crash.

To general, it can be said that integration of secondary nanofillers is a good way to enhance the mechanical properties of PA composites; however the percentage and type of filler play a crucial point.

References

- [1] J. M. Garcés, D. J. Moll, J. Bicerano, R. Fibiger, and D. G. McLeod, 'Polymeric Nanocomposites for Automotive Applications', *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 12, no. 23, pp. 1835–1839, 2000.
- [2] Claude Duval, 'Plastiques et automobile - D'aujourd'hui à demain'. Techniques de l'ingénieur, 10-Jul-2007.
- [3] D. Schmidt, D. Shah, and E. P. Giannelis, 'New advances in polymer/layered silicate nanocomposites', *Curr. Opin. Solid State Mater. Sci.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 205–212, Jun. 2002.
- [4] James Njuguna, Francesco Silva, and Sophia Sachse, 'Nanocomposites for Vehicle Structural Applications', in *Nanofibers - Production, Properties and Functional Applications*, Tong Lin Ed., 2011.
- [5] C.B. Ng, L.S. Schadler, and R.W. Siegel, 'Synthesis and mechanical properties of TiO₂-epoxy nanocomposites', *Nanostructured Mater.*, vol. 12, no. 1–4, pp. 507–510, 1999.
- [6] F. Yang, Y. Ou, and Z. Yu, 'Polyamide 6/silica nanocomposites prepared by in situ polymerization', *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 355–361, 1998.
- [7] A. K. Subramaniyan and C. T. Sun, 'Toughening polymeric composites using nanoclay: Crack tip scale effects on fracture toughness', *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 34–43, Jan. 2007.
- [8] Q. Zhang, Q. Fu, L. Jiang, and Y. Lei, 'Preparation and properties of polypropylene/montmorillonite layered nanocomposites', *Polym. Int.*, vol. 49, no. 12, pp. 1561–1564, 2000.
- [9] Jian-kang Chen, Zhu-ping Huang, and Jue Zhu, 'Size effect of particles on the damage dissipation in nanocomposites', *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 14, pp. 2993–2996, Nov. 2007.
- [10] S.-H. Wu, F.-Y. Wang, C.-C. M. Ma, W.-C. Chang, C.-T. Kuo, H.-C. Kuan, and W.-J. Chen, 'Mechanical, thermal and morphological properties of glass fiber and carbon fiber reinforced polyamide-6 and polyamide-6/clay nanocomposites', *Mater. Lett.*, vol. 49, no. 6, pp. 327–333, Jul. 2001.
- [11] Francesco SILVA, Huijin Zhu, and James Njuguna, 'Mechanical properties and impact-energy absorption of injection moulded nanocomposites structures', presented at the ECCM15-15th European Conference on Composite Materials, Venice, Italy, 2012.